

POWDER DIFFRACTION FROM A COMBINATORIAL AND ANALYTIC VIEWPOINT¹

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Abstract

We consider a variety of estimates on averages of Fourier transforms of measures arising in connection with the Erdős/Falconer distance problem in the setting of powder diffraction experiments in X-ray crystallography, focusing on the connection between the harmonic-analytic and combinatorial work on the one hand, and the physics of powder diffraction on the other.

1. Introduction

Powder diffraction is one of the most widely used material characterization methods. Over the last 50 years it has been used for crystalline phase “finger-printing” in a variety of databases, such as [19]. Recently, cheap and powerful computers, and 2nd and 3rd generation X-ray synchrotron sources have transformed powder diffraction into a very potent structural tool.

The principal scheme of operation of a powder diffractometer consists in studying the angular distribution of the intensity of the scattered X-ray monochromatic beam of wavelength λ , on the atomic length scale of some $10^{-8}cm$, after passing through crystalline powder. The intensity distribution obtained thereby is essentially one-dimensional, characterised by the scattering angle $\theta \in [0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$, due to the fact that the multitude of mini-crystals in the powder have random spatial orientations. It is given by the Debye scattering formula

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$$I(k) = \sum_{i,j} f_i f_j \frac{\sin(kr_{ij})}{kr_{ij}}, \tag{1.1}$$

where

$$k = 4\pi\lambda^{-1} \sin \theta$$

changes from zero essentially to infinity over the range of θ , as the wavelength λ is small. The sum is taken over all pairs of atoms in the sample, r_{ij} are distances between atoms, and the quantities f_i and f_j , called scattering functions, are in general functions of λ but can often be regarded in the above formula as constants termed scattering lengths – we shall further consider the latter case only.

The distribution $I(k)$ is characterised by a series of peaks that encode information about the crystal lattice symmetry group, as well as its defects. “Peak analysis” is today’s key method of processing the diffraction data. From the physics point of view, the principal limitation of powder diffraction is the fact that a three-dimensional set of spots that would arise from a “single crystal” X-ray diffraction experiment is condensed into one dimension in powder diffraction experiments due to angular averaging. Thus, crystal symmetry cannot be seen directly from the powder diffraction pattern. Technically this creates a problem of so-called “peak overlaps” and makes the analysis of the powder diffraction experimental data a separate field involved in its own right. See, for example, [1] and [2] for the state of the art discussion.

The purpose of this article is to present a general mathematical perspective on the theory of the n -dimensional² powder diffraction intensity function and connect it to the classical Erdős/Falconer distance problem in combinatorics and harmonic analysis. In the sequel, we review and conceptualize several important estimates of the intensity function, some with and others without proofs. This paper will introduce the reader to the extensive body of mathematical literature on the subject, and some most recent results are presented here for the first time.

Our basic object of study is a sample, represented by a set $E \subset \mathbb{R}^n$. The length scales are chosen so that E is approximately 1-separated if discrete or is scaled into the unit cube $[0, 1]^n$ if continuous. First we will consider the case when E is a discrete set, and we later move on to the continuous case. In both situations, μ_E is a normalized measure supported on E . In the discrete case, μ_E is the sum of δ -functions, normalized by the number of elements in E . In the continuous case it is typically a density function, whose integral over E equals one. What physicists often refer to as the *structure function* of E is represented by the Fourier transform

$$F_E(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \int e^{-2\pi i \boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \mathbf{x}} d\mu_E(\mathbf{x}). \tag{1.2}$$

²We keep n as a parameter to emphasize that the results presented are not confined to the case $n = 3$. Moreover, from the mathematical point of view, the most difficult dimension is $n = 2$, while the case $n \geq 4$ may be easier. See the discussion in the main body of the paper.

Since only the absolute value of $F_E(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ is observable in a diffraction experiment, define

$$I_E(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = |F_E(\boldsymbol{\xi})|^2, \tag{1.3}$$

a non-negative real-valued function, to be the n -dimensional “single crystal” intensity function. Our objective is to show how the structure of E is encoded into certain averages of the intensity function. In particular, within a class of sets E under consideration, which ones maximize the value of the intensity function $I_E(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ in a suitable sense?

We shall mainly study the *spherical average*

$$\sigma_E(r) = \int I_E(r\boldsymbol{x})d\omega_{\boldsymbol{x}} \tag{1.4}$$

where $d\omega_{\boldsymbol{x}}$ is the surface area measure on the unit sphere S^{n-1} in the reciprocal space, show that it in essence coincides with the powder diffraction intensity function given by the Debye formula (1.1) and point out the mathematical origin of different terms therein. Spherical averages of the squares of the Fourier transforms of measures are part of the core of harmonic analysis, and have numerous applications in number theory and related disciplines. See for example, [18], [16], and the references contained therein.

Observe that the spherical average $\sigma_E(r)$ is interesting only for suitably large r , as I_E equals 1 at the origin (the integral $\int d\mu_E$) and approximately 1 for small r , by the uncertainty principle.

If the set E is in some sense random, one expects the spherical average $\sigma_E(r)$ to be quite regular in the sense that it tends to 0 as $r^{-\beta}$ for some $\beta \in (0, n)$ which is determined by the Hausdorff dimension of E (in the case E is discrete, there is a discrete analog, see [13]). On the flip side, if the set E possesses some translation-invariant structure, the quantity $\sigma_E(r)$ displays peaks, which are usually narrow and well separated from one another to ensure that on average over large intervals of r , the spherical average still has mean decay $\sim r^{-\beta}$. However the point-wise estimate $\sigma_E(r) \leq \text{const.}r^{-\beta}$ for all $r > 1$ is no longer valid.

We will show the immediate connection between the spherical average $\sigma_E(r)$ and Debye’s formula (1.1), with merely $k \sim r$. Hence, point-wise study of the quantity $\sigma_E(r)$ underlies the peak analysis, performed by physicists in order to document or identify different crystalline phases. Namely, the quantity $\sigma_E(r)$ is analyzed point-wise. From the mathematical point of view, point-wise analysis of functions is most difficult, and is often eschewed in favor of certain averages, or moments. If we extend the function $\sigma_E(r)$ to the whole space \mathbb{R}^n by viewing it as a radially symmetric function of $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, then let for $l = 1, 2, \dots$

$$M_{E,2l} = \int \sigma_E^{2l}(\boldsymbol{\xi})d\boldsymbol{\xi} = \int_0^\infty \sigma_E^{2l}(r)r^{n-1}dr \tag{1.5}$$

if the integrals converge. If they do not, we will restrict integration to the interval of length $R \gg 1$ in the last integral and study the dependence of the result on the parameter R . Physically, R has the order of magnitude of one over the X-ray wavelength.

We will show that the *second moment* $M_{E,2}$ (corresponding to $l = 1$) represents a very important characteristic of the *distance set* of E , defined as

$$\Delta(E) = \{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\| : \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in E\}, \quad (1.6)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean distance. In particular, the greater $M_{E,2}$, the smaller the distance set $\Delta(E)$ may be. In the discrete case, if E is a “typical” set of N elements, one can expect to have some $N(N-1)/2$ distinct distances in the distance set $\Delta(E)$. However, if E is translation-invariant, the distance set gets considerably smaller. It is conjectured that of all the discrete sets of N elements (clearly modulo rigid motions and scalings), the minimum number of distances occurs in the case of the $\sqrt[n]{N} \times \dots \times \sqrt[n]{N}$ integer grid.

The fourth and higher moments of the spherical average also turn out to be indicative of translation-invariant structure, and perhaps in a more explicit way than the second moment. To this effect, we shall show that if the $2l$ th, for $l = 2, 3, \dots$ moment is large enough, then the set belongs to a finite union of lattices. As a counterpart to this result, we shall show that sets with no translation-invariant structure have small fourth moments.

So, the “physics” message of this paper is that moments the intensity function should be still sensitive to the fundamental geometric properties of the sample set E and hence useful for material fingerprinting and related purposes whenever powder diffraction is involved. While they contain less general information than the whole function $\sigma_E(r)$, they are easier to compute, store and compare, and, being averages, are relatively insensitive to noise and other errors.

This paper is organized as follows. The first section deals with the discrete case, with allusions to the Erdős distance conjecture [4] which has been a major unsolved problem in geometrical combinatorics since 1946. In Section 3 we will study the continuous case when the set E is characterized by the Hausdorff dimension $\alpha \in (0, n)$. Throughout the discussion we attempt to emphasize the synthesis of the ideas we present.

2. Discrete Case

In this section we operate on the length scale where an average distance between the atoms in the sample studied is approximately one.

We shall make use of the following terminology.

Definition 2.1. An infinite discrete set $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is a *Delaunay* (alias Delone) set if

- i. there exists a constant $c_A > 0$ such that $\|\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}'\| \geq c_A$ for every pair of different elements $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}' \in A$,
- ii. there exists a constant $C_A > c_A$ such that every cube of side-length C_A contains at least one element of A .

Let $q \gg 1$ be an asymptotic parameter and $A_q = A \cap [0, q]^n$ be a truncation of A , i.e., the sample set E is $\frac{1}{q}A_q$. In view of the general discussion in the introduction, the corresponding measure, normalized by the number of elements $|A_q|$ is

$$\mu_{A_q} = \frac{1}{|A_q|} \sum_{\mathbf{a} \in A} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{a}), \tag{2.1}$$

resulting in the intensity function

$$I_{A_q}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \frac{1}{|A_q|^2} \left| \sum_{\mathbf{a} \in A_q} e^{2\pi i \mathbf{a} \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}} \right|^2.$$

It is furthermore convenient however (due to the fact that the diameter of A_q is $O(q)$ rather than 1) to multiply the intensity by $|A_q|$, so we shall further refer to its definition as follows:

$$I_{A_q}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \frac{1}{|A_q|} \left| \sum_{\mathbf{a} \in A_q} e^{2\pi i \mathbf{a} \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}} \right|^2 = \frac{1}{|A_q|} \sum_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}' \in A_q} e^{2\pi i (\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}') \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}}. \tag{2.2}$$

2.1. Averaging

We are now ready to introduce different types of averages of the intensity function. We start out with the trivial case of the so-called *solid average*: for $R \gg 1$ let

$$\bar{I}_{A_q} = \frac{1}{c_n R^n} \int_{R \leq \|\boldsymbol{\xi}\| \leq 2R} I_{A_q}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\boldsymbol{\xi} = \frac{c_\psi}{c_n R^n} \int I_{A_q}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \psi(\boldsymbol{\xi}/R) d\boldsymbol{\xi}. \tag{2.3}$$

The constant c_n above is the volume of the unit ball in \mathbb{R}^n ; in the sequel the value of c_n may vary, but will depend on the dimension only, and can easily be computed for any practical purpose, generally being related to volumes of unit balls and spheres and various integration constants. In addition, the integration in (2.3) has been extended to the whole \mathbb{R}^n by incorporating a radially symmetric (henceforth we will simply say *radial*) infinitely differentiable “cutoff” (alias “test”) function³, which in (2.3) is identically equal to 1 in the spherical shell $\|\mathbf{x}\| \in [1, 2]$ and vanishes outside a slightly larger shell, say $\|\mathbf{x}\| \in [.9, 2.1]$. Hence, the appearance of the constant c_ψ , which is once again $O(1)$ and computable.

For simplicity we shall often suppress such “geometric” constants c_n as well as “cutoff function” constants c_ψ (both may change from line to line, as well as the universal notation ψ for various cutoff functions use, yet they are always independent of the asymptotic parameters) by using in equation the \simeq symbol instead of the equality. We shall also absorb the

³Cutoff C^∞ functions are routinely used further in the paper, always being denoted as ψ . One can also use Gaussians as cutoff functions. In both cases the “tails” beyond the effective supports of the functions themselves or their Fourier transforms are negligible and will not be estimated.

“Delaunay” constants C_A and c_A into the proportionality symbol \simeq but will point out when they matter. Hence, the pre-factor in (2.2)

$$\frac{1}{|A_q|} \simeq q^{-n},$$

yet it depends on C_A, c_A .

In the same fashion we shall use the symbols \lesssim and \gtrsim to suppress such constants in inequalities. Finally, the \approx symbol will be used to avoid constants as well as to drop “trivial” terms in sums and integrals involved: in general $X \approx Y$ if $X \lesssim Y$ and $Y \lesssim X$.

With this notational convention, writing out the definition of I_{A_q} in (2.3), we see that

$$\bar{I}_{A_q} \simeq \frac{1}{|A_q|} \sum_{\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}' \in A_q} \widehat{\psi}(R(\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}')), \tag{2.4}$$

where

$$\widehat{\psi}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-2\pi i \mathbf{x} \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}} \psi(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x},$$

the Fourier transform of ψ . By the uncertainty principle, $\widehat{\psi}(R(\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}'))$ is concentrated in the set

$$\{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}') \in A_q \times A_q : \|\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}'\| \leq c_\psi R^{-1}\}.$$

That, for large R , leaves out the case $\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{a}'$ in the double sum in (2.4), i.e.

$$\bar{I}_{A_q} \simeq 1.$$

As far as the solid average is concerned, all Delaunay sets of the same density are the same.

In order to obtain a more interesting dependence on geometry, consider the *spherical average*

$$\sigma_{A_q}(r) = \int I_{A_q}(r\mathbf{x}) d\omega_{\mathbf{x}}, \tag{2.5}$$

where the integral is taken with respect to the surface measure on the unit sphere.

We now average over the range $r \lesssim q$. By the uncertainty principle, this would correspond to the case when the actual atom size, as well as the wavelength λ are of order q^{-1} – on the scale when the atomic spacing is of order 1, so physically, if the sample gets scaled into $O(1)$, we would have $q^{-2} \sim 10^{-8} \text{cm}$. As we have mentioned earlier, the quantity $\sigma_{A_q}(r)$ is not interesting for small r , so we can once again fix a smooth cut-off function ψ (this time of one variable on the non-negative real axis), such that $\psi(r) \equiv 1$ for $r \in [0, 1]$ and vanishes for $r > 1.1$. Let the *second moment*

$$M_{A_q,2} = \frac{1}{q^n} \int_0^\infty \sigma_{A_q}^2(r) \widehat{\psi}(r/q) r^{n-1} dr, \tag{2.6}$$

cf. (1.5) Observe that the presence of the cutoff function ψ in the integral effectively means that integration is performed in the range $r \lesssim q$, hence the factor $\frac{1}{q^n}$ plays the normalization role.

In order to understand the meaning of the second moment, let us introduce the *distance multiplicity function* by the formula

$$m_{\frac{1}{q}}(r) = \# \left\{ (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}') : r \leq \|\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}'\| \leq r + \frac{1}{q} \right\}. \tag{2.7}$$

The main result in this section is the following theorem.

Theorem 2.2. *We have*

$$M_{A_q,2} \approx 1 + G_q, \quad \text{where} \tag{2.8}$$

$$G_q = \frac{1}{q^{3n-1}} \sum_r \left(\frac{m_{\frac{1}{q}}(r)}{r^{\frac{n-1}{2}}} \right)^2,$$

with the sum being taken over a maximal $\frac{1}{q}$ -separated subset of $\Delta(A_q) \setminus 0$.

Before we present the proof of Theorem 2.2, let us point out that the quantity under the summation sign is calculated as follows. For each $\mathbf{a} \in A_q$ one takes a spherical shell of radius r and thickness $\frac{1}{q}$ centered at the point \mathbf{a} and counts the number of elements of A_q in this shell, weighted by $r^{\frac{1-n}{2}}$. Then the summation over the choice of the center \mathbf{a} is effected. Further, the result gets squared and summed over all r 's which are multiples of $\frac{1}{q}$.

The formula (2.8) shows that $M_{A_q,2}$ tends to get larger when the distance multiplicity function $m_{\frac{1}{q}}(r)$ deviates a lot from its expected value, which as it's easy to see is approximately $q^n \cdot (q^{-1}r^{n-1})$. Hence, if the set A_q is random, one can expect that

$$G_q \approx q^{-3n+1} \cdot q^{2n-2} \cdot q \int_0^q r^{n-1} dr \approx 1. \tag{2.9}$$

However, if A has a translation-invariant structure, the distance multiplicity function $m_{\frac{1}{q}}(r)$ can deviate from its expected value considerably, at least for $n = 2, 3$.

Remark 2.3. In particular, if $A = \mathbb{Z}^n$, it is well known that the quantity $q^{-n}m_{\frac{1}{q}}(r)$ can be as large as some quantity $d_n(r)$, which for $n = 2$ equals the maximum number of divisors an integer r can have (which is asymptotically smaller any positive power of r but greater than any power of $\log r$). For $n = 3$ it can be as large as $r \log r$. For $n = 4$ it is $O(r^2)$. For $n \geq 5$ it is known that if a sphere of radius r has an integer point on it, the total number of points of \mathbb{Z}^n is guaranteed to be $\approx r^{n-2}$. See [14] and [9] for details.

For the practical purpose of processing the powder diffraction data, an experimental outcome when the quantity (2.8) is fairly small, should signal the lack of translation-invariant

structure in the sample. On the other hand, different types of crystal structure should yield different values of the second moment. In particular, its value for the cubical lattice largely exceeds the value one gets for the tetrahedral lattice. The latter, although optimal from the packing point of view, is far from optimal from the point of view of the distance multiplicity function second moment.

2.2. Proof of Theorem 2.2

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{A_q}(r) &= \int I_{A_q}(r\mathbf{x})d\omega_{\mathbf{x}} \\ &= c_n + q^{-n} \sum_{\mathbf{a}\neq\mathbf{a}'} \int e^{2\pi i(\mathbf{a}-\mathbf{a}')\cdot r\mathbf{x}}d\omega_{\mathbf{x}} \\ &= c_n + q^{-n} \sum_{\mathbf{a}\neq\mathbf{a}'} \widehat{\omega}(r(\mathbf{a}-\mathbf{a}')). \end{aligned} \tag{2.10}$$

Henceforth, $\widehat{\omega}$ denotes the Fourier transform of the surface measure on the unit sphere.

A well-known calculation yields

$$\widehat{\omega}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = 2\pi \frac{J_{\frac{n}{2}-1}(\|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|)}{\|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|^{\frac{n-1}{2}}},$$

where $J_{\frac{n}{2}-1}$ is the Bessel function of order $\frac{n}{2} - 1$. However, this formula will not be used further, except the following remark.

Remark 2.4. In the case $n = 3$, we have

$$J_{\frac{n}{2}-1}(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi x}} \sin x,$$

and therefore the quantity $\sigma_{A_q}(r)$ does give us the Debye formula (1.1), where all the scattering lengths f_i were equal. Clearly, this can be adapted to the case of different scattering lengths by introducing weights into the measure (2.1).

Note that the first term in (2.10) corresponds to the choice $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}'$ in the intensity definition (2.2). The constant c_n is now the surface area of the unit sphere, to be absorbed into the \approx symbol, i.e we'll further assume $\widehat{\omega}(\mathbf{0}) = 1$.

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} M_{A_q,2} &\approx 1 + q^{-2n} \sum_{\mathbf{a}\neq\mathbf{a}'} \int_0^\infty \widehat{\omega}(r(\mathbf{a}-\mathbf{a}'))r^{n-1}\psi(r/q)dr \\ &+ q^{-3n} \sum_{\mathbf{a}\neq\mathbf{a}';\mathbf{b}\neq\mathbf{b}'} \int_0^\infty \widehat{\omega}(r(\mathbf{a}-\mathbf{a}'))\widehat{\omega}(r(\mathbf{b}-\mathbf{b}'))\psi^2(r/q)r^{n-1}dr \\ &= 1 + Y_q + X_q. \end{aligned}$$

To evaluate that quantity Y_q let us view the test function ψ as a radial function of a variable $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, rewrite the integral for Y_q as an integral over \mathbb{R}^n and apply Plancherel's theorem

$$\int \widehat{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi})\widehat{g}(\boldsymbol{\xi})d\boldsymbol{\xi} = \int f(\boldsymbol{x})g(\boldsymbol{x})d\boldsymbol{x}$$

and the convolution theorem

$$\widehat{f\widehat{g}} = \widehat{f * g}, \text{ where } f * g(\boldsymbol{x}) = \int f(\boldsymbol{x} - \boldsymbol{y})g(\boldsymbol{y})d\boldsymbol{y}.$$

We get

$$\begin{aligned} q^{2n}Y_q &\simeq \sum_{\boldsymbol{a} \neq \boldsymbol{a}'} \int \widehat{\omega}(\boldsymbol{\xi} \|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|)\psi(\boldsymbol{\xi}/q)d\boldsymbol{\xi} \\ &= \sum_{\boldsymbol{a} \neq \boldsymbol{a}'} \frac{q^n}{\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|^{n-1}} \int \int \left(\int \widehat{\psi}[q(\boldsymbol{x} - \boldsymbol{y})]d\omega_{\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|^{-1}\boldsymbol{y}} \right) d\boldsymbol{x}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.11}$$

Above, $d\omega_{\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|^{-1}\boldsymbol{y}}$ is the surface measure on the sphere of radius $\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|$. Hence, we integrate first in \boldsymbol{x} , and for each \boldsymbol{y} we have the following situation. By the uncertainty principle, the Fourier transform of the test function $\psi(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ is a radial function which vanishes faster than any inverse power of the distance from the origin. Effectively, one can substitute $\widehat{\psi}$ by the characteristic function of the unit ball. Then, for each \boldsymbol{y} , integration in \boldsymbol{x} can be effectively restricted to the ball of radius $\frac{1}{q}$ around \boldsymbol{y} . Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} q^{2n}Y_q &\simeq \sum_{\boldsymbol{a} \neq \boldsymbol{a}'} \frac{1}{\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|^{n-1}} \int d\omega_{\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|^{-1}\boldsymbol{y}} \\ &= \sum_{\boldsymbol{a} \neq \boldsymbol{a}'} 1 \simeq q^{2n}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.12}$$

It follows that $Y_q = O(1)$.

The quantity X_q is evaluated in the same way. To simplify matters, there is no harm writing $\psi(r/q)$ instead of $\psi^2(r/q)$ in the integral for X_q , by the properties of the test function ψ . Then writing the integral as an integral over \mathbb{R}^n and applying the Plancherel theorem and the convolution theorem we have

$$\begin{aligned} q^{3n}X_q &\simeq \sum_{\boldsymbol{a} \neq \boldsymbol{a}', \boldsymbol{b} \neq \boldsymbol{b}'} \int (\widehat{\omega}[\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|\boldsymbol{\xi}]\psi(\boldsymbol{\xi}/q))^\wedge(\boldsymbol{x}) \cdot (\widehat{\omega}[\|\boldsymbol{b} - \boldsymbol{b}'\|\boldsymbol{\xi}])^\wedge(\boldsymbol{x})d\boldsymbol{x} \\ &= \sum_{\boldsymbol{a} \neq \boldsymbol{a}', \boldsymbol{b} \neq \boldsymbol{b}'} \frac{1}{(\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|\|\boldsymbol{b} - \boldsymbol{b}'\|)^{n-1}} \int [d\omega_{\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|^{-1}\boldsymbol{y}} * (q^n\psi(q\boldsymbol{y}))](\boldsymbol{x})d\omega_{\|\boldsymbol{b} - \boldsymbol{b}'\|^{-1}\boldsymbol{x}} \\ &\simeq \sum_{\boldsymbol{a} \neq \boldsymbol{a}', \boldsymbol{b} \neq \boldsymbol{b}'} \frac{1}{(\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|\|\boldsymbol{b} - \boldsymbol{b}'\|)^{n-1}} \int_{\mathcal{S}(\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|, \frac{1}{q})} q d\omega_{\|\boldsymbol{b} - \boldsymbol{b}'\|^{-1}\boldsymbol{x}} \\ &\simeq q \sum_r \left(\frac{m_{\frac{1}{q}}(r)}{r^{\frac{n-1}{2}}} \right)^2, \end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

with the sum over r being taken over a maximal $\frac{1}{q}$ -separated subset of $\Delta(A_q) \setminus \{0\}$. Above, $\mathcal{S}(\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|, \frac{1}{q})$ denotes a spherical shell of radius $\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|$ and thickness $\frac{1}{q}$.

Indeed, $\omega_{\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|^{-1}\boldsymbol{y}}$ is the surface measure on the sphere of radius $\|\boldsymbol{a} - \boldsymbol{a}'\|$, and its convolution with $q^n\psi(q\boldsymbol{y})$ (which as has been done in the estimate for Y_q , can be thought to

be supported in the ball of radius $\frac{1}{q}$ and apart from that integrates into approximately one) is effectively a density, supported in the shell $\mathcal{S}(\|\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}'\|, \frac{1}{q})$, of the value of approximately q . As $d\omega_{\|\mathbf{b}-\mathbf{b}'\|^{-1}\mathbf{x}}$ is the surface measure on the sphere of radius $\|\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{b}'\|$, the integral in the penultimate line of (2.13) will be non-zero only if

$$\left| \|\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}'\| - \|\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{b}'\| \right| \lesssim \frac{1}{q}.$$

So we can set $\|\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}'\| = \|\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{b}'\| = r$, and furthermore, r can be assumed to run through a discrete sequence of values $r_j = \frac{j}{q}$, $j = 1, \dots, q^2$. Now r being fixed, the quantity

$$\sum_{\mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{a}', \mathbf{b} \neq \mathbf{b}'} \int_{\mathcal{S}(\|\mathbf{a}-\mathbf{a}'\|, \frac{1}{q})} d\omega_{\|\mathbf{b}-\mathbf{b}'\|^{-1}\mathbf{x}}$$

can be replaced by the square of the quantity $m_{\frac{1}{q}}(r)$, which has been defined by (2.7). This proves Theorem 2.2. Observe that due to the fact that as the claim involves the maximum $\frac{1}{q}$ -separated subset of the distance set of A_q , the constants hidden in the formulae in Theorem 2.2 should depend on the Delaunay constants C_A, c_A .

2.3. Connections with Geometric Combinatorics

We start out by briefly recalling basic definitions from the theory of distance sets. See, for example, [17] and the references contained therein for a thorough treatment of this subject.

Let A be a Delaunay set. Define $\Delta(A_q)$, following (1.6). The *Erdős Distance Conjecture* (EDC) says that

$$|\Delta(A_q)| \geq c_\epsilon q^{2-\epsilon}, \tag{2.14}$$

for any $\epsilon > 0$ and where $|A|$ or $\#A$ denote cardinality of a finite set.

In the case when $A = \mathbb{Z}^n$, the classic number theory calculation (see for example [14] and [9]) shows that

$$|\Delta(A_q)| \approx \frac{q^2}{\sqrt{\log(q)}} \text{ when } n = 2,$$

and

$$|\Delta(A_q)| \approx q^2 \text{ when } n \geq 3.$$

In particular, in the case $n = 2$ the squares of the distances are those integers in the interval $[0, 2q^2]$, which can be represented as sums of two squares. The average density of such integers in the interval above is proportional to $\frac{q^2}{\sqrt{\log(q)}}$.

A possible approach to EDC, exploited by several authors in recent years, is the following. Let

$$m(r) = \#\{(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{a}') \in A_q \times A_q : \|\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}'\| = r\}, \tag{2.15}$$

cf. (2.7).

Suppose that we could show that

$$\sum_{t \in \Delta(A_q) \setminus 0} m^2(r)t^{-(n-1)} \leq C_\epsilon q^{3n-1+\epsilon}. \tag{2.16}$$

Since

$$\sum_{t \in \Delta(A_q) \setminus 0} m(r) \approx q^{2n}, \tag{2.17}$$

by definition of $m(r)$, the Cauchy-Schwartz inequality implies that

$$\begin{aligned} q^{4n} &\approx \left(\sum_{t \in \Delta(A_q) \setminus 0} m(r) \cdot 1 \right)^2 \\ &\leq \sum_{t \in \Delta(A_q) \setminus 0} 1 \cdot \sum_{t \in \Delta(A_q) \setminus 0} m^2(r)[q^{n-1}t^{-(n-1)}] \\ &\leq C_\epsilon q^{4n-2+\epsilon} \cdot |\Delta(A_q)|, \end{aligned} \tag{2.18}$$

and EDC follows.

Equivalently, in the notation of Theorem 2.2, if we assume that $M_{A_q,2} \leq C_\epsilon q^\epsilon$, we are guaranteed to have at least $C_\epsilon^{-1} q^{2-\epsilon}$ distinct distances in the distance set $\Delta(A_q)$, which are, moreover, separated by $\frac{c}{q}$, where c depends on the Delaunay constants c_A and C_A .

2.4. Maximum Intensity Conjecture

Theorem 2.2 and the argument in the estimates (2.16–2.18) in the previous section suggest that the distance set estimate (2.14) would follow from the upper bound

$$M_{A_q,2} \leq C_\epsilon q^\epsilon. \tag{2.19}$$

The quantity $M_{A_q,2}$ can be computed explicitly in cases when the underlying set A possesses translational symmetry. Further in this section we shall do it for the lattice \mathbb{Z}^n .

This leads us to conjecture that in the class \mathcal{A} of Delaunay sets under consideration, one should not only have (2.19), but

$$\sup_{A \in \mathcal{A}} M_{A_q,2} \lesssim M_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n,2}, \tag{2.20}$$

as well, where $\mathbb{Z}_q^n = \mathbb{Z}^n \cap [0, q]^n$.

We shall further refer to this conjecture as the *Maximum Intensity Conjecture* (MIC). The Maximum Intensity Conjecture would immediately lead to the resolution of the Erdős Distance Conjecture for Delaunay sets.

If we accept the Maximum Intensity Conjecture, we can deduce the EDC if we can show that

$$M_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n,2} \leq C_\epsilon q^\epsilon. \tag{2.21}$$

This fact results immediately from Theorem 2.2, the calculation (2.9) that follows it and Remark 2.3. Note that according to Remark 2.3, dimensions 4 and higher would allow for $\epsilon = 0$. It is not clear whether for $n = 3$ one can strengthen (2.21) to $M_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n,2} \lesssim 1$. On the one hand, the best one can prove is that $M_{\mathbb{Z}_q^3,2} \lesssim \log q$ (see Remark 2.3). Yet it is known that $\#\Delta(\mathbb{Z}_q^3) \gtrsim q^2$. Hence it is not clear whether $\log q$ is intrinsic or is an artifact of the Cauchy-Schwartz inequality application in (2.18) and the supremum estimate $q^3 r \log r$ for the quantity $m_{\frac{1}{q}}(r)$.

In fact, it is easy to show that

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n}(r) &\lesssim \frac{q}{r}, && \text{for } r \geq 1, n \geq 4, \\ \sigma_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n}(r) &\leq C_\epsilon \frac{q}{r^{1-\epsilon}}, && \text{for } r \geq 1, n = 2, 3. \end{aligned} \tag{2.22}$$

First off, note that from (2.10), for $r \lesssim \frac{1}{q}$ we have $\sigma_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n}(r) \approx q^n$. Observe that the contribution of the interval $r \lesssim \frac{1}{q}$ into (2.6) is then $O(1)$.

Now let us assume $r \gtrsim \frac{1}{q}$. Return to (2.10) where we can drop the first term and use the translational invariance of the lattice to reduce the double sum to a one index sum as follows:

$$\sigma_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n}(r) \approx \sum_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{Z}_q^n} \widehat{\omega}(r\mathbf{a}) \approx \sum_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{Z}^n} \widehat{\omega}(r\mathbf{a}) \widehat{\psi}(\mathbf{a}/q). \tag{2.23}$$

Above, we have extended the summation over the whole lattice \mathbb{Z}^n by using a radial test function ψ , which is supported in the unit ball and is identically one in unit ball of radius, say $\frac{1}{3}$. Without loss of generality $\widehat{\psi}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ can be thought to be non-negative (e.g. ψ can be chosen as a convolution of some radial function with itself) and by the uncertainty principle it vanishes faster than any power of $\|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|$ beyond the unit ball. Now we can apply the Poisson summation formula and the convolution theorem to obtain

$$\sigma_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n}(r) \lesssim \frac{1}{r^{n-1}} \sum_{\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{Z}^n} \int q^d \psi[q(\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{x})] d\omega_{r^{-1}\mathbf{x}} \simeq \frac{q}{r^{n-1}} \#\{\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{Z}^n : \|\mathbf{a}\| = r\}. \tag{2.24}$$

Remark 2.3 gives one the upper bound for the number of the lattice points on the sphere of radius r . Namely

$$\#\{\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{Z}^n : \|\mathbf{a}\| = r\} \leq r^{n-2}$$

in $n \geq 4$, with the slightly weaker bound in lower dimension. This proves the estimate (2.22)

which in turn immediately implies that

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n, 2} &\lesssim 1, & \text{for } n \geq 4, \\ M_{\mathbb{Z}_q^n, 2} &\leq C_\epsilon q^\epsilon, & \text{for } n = 2, 3. \end{aligned} \tag{2.25}$$

3. Continuous Case

Let us now discuss the continuous situation. The general set-up is the compact set $E \subset [0, 1]^n$, of dimension $\alpha \in (0, n)$. The “physical” definition of dimension would be the existence of an Ahlfors-David regular measure supported on E – suppose that there exists a measure μ supported on E , such that for any \mathbf{x} in the support of μ , one has

$$\mu(B(\mathbf{x}, \delta)) \approx \delta^\alpha, \tag{3.1}$$

for all sufficiently small $\delta > 0$; the notation $B(\mathbf{x}, \delta)$ stands for a n -dimensional ball of the radius δ centered at \mathbf{x} .

Physically however, $\delta \rightarrow 0$ should mean that $\delta \geq \delta_0$, the latter being, say the atomic size. From this point of view, the set $E = \frac{1}{q}A_q$ (i.e A_q , which gets scaled into the unit cube) discussed in the previous section has dimension $\alpha = \frac{n}{2}$, and $\delta_0 \approx q^{-2}$, the atomic length scale and the length scale of the X-rays. Indeed, we can construct the measure μ as follows. Let $\psi(\mathbf{x})$ be the characteristic function of the unit ball. Let

$$d\mu_q(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{|A_q|} \sum_{\mathbf{a} \in \frac{1}{q}A_q} [q^{2n}\psi(q^2\mathbf{x})]d\mathbf{x}. \tag{3.2}$$

Then $\int d\mu_q(\mathbf{x}) \simeq 1$ and it is an easy calculation to verify that the definition (3.1) is satisfied with $\alpha = \frac{n}{2}$, for $\delta \gtrsim \frac{1}{q^2}$. Recall that this dimension corresponded to “thickening” each point of A_q into a ball of radius $\simeq \frac{1}{q}$, or the “physical” assumptions that atomic sizes are some q times smaller than the spacing between the atoms. If one substitutes $[q^{2n}\psi(q^2\mathbf{x})]$ in the formula (3.2) with $q^{\frac{n^2}{\alpha}}\psi(q^{\frac{n}{\alpha}}\mathbf{x})$, one would get a “fractal” measure of dimension α in the sense that the definition (3.1) holds for all $\delta \gtrsim q^{-\frac{n}{\alpha}}$. Moreover, if one denotes E_q the support of the measure μ_q , then after taking a sequence of q 's, which rapidly enough goes to infinity, the set $\bigcap_q E_q$ will represent a bona fide fractal of dimension α , with the bona fide fractal measure μ_∞ on it (obtained as a limit of the measures μ_q), which satisfies (3.1) for all $1 > \delta > 0$. See [6] for details.

Conversely, if one takes the fractal measure μ_∞ and convolves it with the quantity $q^{\frac{n^2}{\alpha}}\psi(q^{\frac{n}{\alpha}}\mathbf{x})$ (which integrates approximately into one) the density resulting from the convolution will satisfy (3.1), but only for $\delta \gtrsim q^{-\frac{n}{\alpha}}$. See [6], [10] for details.

3.1. Falconer Distance Problem

Returning to the general fractal dimensional set up, from (3.1) it follows that the α -energy

$$\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\mu) = \int \int \frac{d\mu_{\mathbf{x}}d\mu_{\mathbf{y}}}{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|^\alpha} = O(1). \tag{3.3}$$

Rewriting (3.3) by Plancherel’s theorem and passing to polar coordinates we obtain

$$\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\mu) = \int \frac{|\widehat{\mu}(\boldsymbol{\xi})|^2}{\|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|^{n-\alpha}} = \int_0^\infty r^{\alpha-1}\sigma_E(r)dr, \tag{3.4}$$

where $\sigma_E(r)$ has been defined by (1.4) and models the observable intensity in power diffraction experiments.

It follows that on average $\sigma_E(r)$ is smaller than $r^{-\alpha}$. However, it does not necessarily happen for all r , as is illustrated, for instance, by an example by Sjölin [20].

By the compactness of $E \subset [0, 1]^d$ it follows that the expression (3.3) will not change in essence if we multiply, say, $d\mu_{\mathbf{x}}$ in (3.3) by a cutoff function $\psi(\mathbf{x})$ which equals 1 on $[0, 1]^d$ and is supported on a slightly larger set. By the convolution theorem and the uncertainty principle, this implies that for $r \gg 1$

$$\sigma_E(r) \simeq \frac{1}{r^{n-1}} \int r^{n-\alpha} \frac{|\widehat{\mu}(\boldsymbol{\xi})|^2}{\|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|^{n-\alpha}} \chi_{\mathcal{S}(r,1)}(\boldsymbol{\xi})d\boldsymbol{\xi} \lesssim r^{1-\alpha}\mathcal{I}_\alpha(\mu).$$

Above, $\chi_{\mathcal{S}(r,1)}$ denotes the characteristic function of the spherical shell $\mathcal{S}(r, 1)$ of radius r and thickness 1.

Hence, one has the general bound

$$\sigma_E(r) \lesssim r^{-\alpha+1}. \tag{3.5}$$

The quantity $\sigma_E(r)$ is closely related to the distance set $\Delta(E)$. To this effect, there is a continuous analog of the Erdős distance conjecture, the Falconer distance problem, [7]. It states that if $\alpha > \frac{n}{2}$, then the Lebesgue measure of the distance set $\Delta(E)$ is positive.

The relation between the spherical average $\sigma_E(r)$ and the distance set $\Delta(E)$ gets established via the machinery developed by Mattila [15]. The discussion in the previous section presented in fact a discrete analog of this machinery; the continuous situation can be summarized as follows.

Mattila proves that for $\alpha \geq \frac{n}{2}$, if

$$M_{E,2} = \int_0^\infty \sigma_E^2(r)r^{n-1}dr < \infty, \tag{3.6}$$

then the Lebesgue measure of $\Delta(E)$ is positive, using the continuous version of the argument in (2.15–2.18). He considers the pull-forward ν on $\Delta(E)$ of the measure $\mu \times \mu$ on $E \times E$,

under the distance map, defined as follows: for a test function $\psi(r)$ on the non-negative real axis,

$$\int \psi(r) d\nu_r = \int \int \psi(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|) d\mu_{\mathbf{x}} d\mu_{\mathbf{y}}.$$

Then by the Cauchy-Schwartz inequality and Plancherel theorem,

$$1 \lesssim \left(\int d\nu_r \right)^2 \leq |\Delta(E)| \cdot \int |\widehat{\nu}(t)|^2 dt, \tag{3.7}$$

as long as ν has an L^2 density. The notation $|\Delta(E)|$ above denotes the Lebesgue measure of the distance set.

Mattila then shows that if $\widehat{\nu}$ denotes the one-dimensional Fourier transform of the distance set measure ν , it turns out that

$$\widehat{\nu}(t) \approx t^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \int |\widehat{\mu}(\boldsymbol{\xi})|^2 d\omega_{\boldsymbol{\xi}}. \tag{3.8}$$

I.e., the spherical average represents a weighted Fourier transform of the distance measure, whose discrete analog is the distance multiplicity function $m(r)$, cf. (2.15). See [15] for details.

Observe that rewriting the integral (3.6) as an integral over \mathbb{R}^n and using the bound (3.5) for $\sigma_E(r)$ it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} M_{E,2} &\lesssim \int |\widehat{\mu}(\boldsymbol{\xi})|^2 \|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|^{-n+(n-\alpha+1)} d\boldsymbol{\xi} \\ &\lesssim \int \int \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|^{-(n-\alpha+1)} d\mu_{\mathbf{x}} d\mu_{\mathbf{y}} \\ &\equiv \mathcal{I}_{n+1-\alpha}(\mu). \end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

This answers affirmatively to the question posed in the Falconer distance problem, provided that $\alpha \geq \frac{n+1}{2}$.

The question arises whether the improvement towards the desired $\alpha > \frac{n}{2}$ can be gained by strengthening the bound (3.5).

The best known result in this direction is due to Wolff [22], in $n = 2$, and Erdoĝan [3] in higher dimensions. The result implies that the Lebesgue measure of $\Delta(E)$ is indeed positive if the Hausdorff dimension of E is greater than $\frac{n}{2} + \frac{1}{3}$.

It is based on the following estimate:

$$\sigma_E(r) \lesssim r^{-\beta}, \quad \forall \beta < \begin{cases} \alpha, & \text{for } \alpha \leq \frac{n-1}{2}, \\ \frac{n-1}{2} & \text{for } \frac{n-1}{2} \leq \alpha \leq \frac{n}{2}, \\ \frac{n+2\alpha-2}{4} & \text{for } \frac{n}{2} \leq \alpha \leq \frac{n+1}{2}. \end{cases} \tag{3.10}$$

It is interesting that due to a counterexample of Sjölin [20] the bounds (3.10) cannot be improved in $n = 2$. However, they are not likely to be optimal for $\alpha > \frac{n}{2}$ and $n \geq 3$. (For measures arising in the context of Delaunay sets, the authors [11] showed the above estimate for $\beta \leq \frac{n-1}{n}\alpha$.) For $n = 3$, Sjölin’s example shows that the Falconer conjecture cannot be resolved by improving the bound (3.10) alone. However, it may be possible (as suggested in [3]) in dimensions $n \geq 4$, cf. Remark 2.3.

3.2. On Additive Structure of Measures

We have shown earlier that the second moment $M_{E,2}$ is indicative of the distance structure of the set E . In this final section we would like to discuss how higher moments are indicative of the presence of additive, or translation-invariant structure and translational symmetry and therefore should represent a certain signature thereof.

We shall content ourselves with the fourth moment $M_{E,4}$ only and point out two principal facts:

- i. Large $M_{E,4}$ indicate the presence of an additive structure;
- ii. The total lack of additive structure results in very small values of $M_{E,4}$; in particular the Falconer conjecture holds for sets with the total lack of additive structure.

See [12] for broader discussion.

Let us first show how the fourth moment is indicative of translations in the critical case of the Hausdorff dimension $\alpha = \frac{n}{2}$.

Define $\mathbf{a} \approx_\delta \mathbf{b}$ if $\|\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{b}\| \leq \delta$. Let $X = (\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$, $Y = (\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ and $\mu^* = \mu_X \times \mu_Y = \mu \times \mu \times \mu \times \mu$.

Suppose, $\psi(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ is a radial cut-off function which is supported in the spherical shell $\{\boldsymbol{\xi} : .9 \leq \|\boldsymbol{\xi}\| \leq 2.1\}$, and is identically one for $1 \leq \|\boldsymbol{\xi}\| \leq 2$. Let $R \gg 1$. Consider the following variation of the fourth moment:

$$M_{E,4}(R) = \int_{R \leq r \leq 2R} \sigma_E^4(r) r^{n-1} dr = \int_{R \leq \|\boldsymbol{\xi}\| \leq 2R} |\widehat{\mu}(\boldsymbol{\xi})|^4 d\boldsymbol{\xi}. \tag{3.11}$$

By the Fubini theorem,

$$\begin{aligned} M_{E,4}(R) &\approx \int \int [\int e^{-2\pi i \mathbf{z} \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}} \psi(\boldsymbol{\xi}/R) d\boldsymbol{\xi}] d\mu_X d\mu_Y \\ &= R^n \int \int \widehat{\psi}(R\mathbf{z}) d\mu_X d\mu_Y, \end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

where $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}_2 - \mathbf{y}_1 - \mathbf{y}_2$. Hence, since $\widehat{\psi}$ decays rapidly, we get

$$M_{E,4}(R) \approx R^n \cdot \mu^* \{(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2) : \mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}_2 \approx_\delta \mathbf{y}_1 + \mathbf{y}_2\}, \tag{3.13}$$

where $\delta \approx \frac{1}{R}$.

Furthermore, the formula (3.1) vindicates the following discretization. Let $q \approx R$ be an integer. There exists a set $\Gamma_q \subset (qE \cap \mathbb{Z}^n)$ of cardinality $\approx q^{\frac{n}{2}}$, such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \mu^* \{(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2) : \mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}_2 \approx_\delta \mathbf{y}_1 + \mathbf{y}_2\} \\ & \approx q^{-2n} \#\{(\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2) \in \Gamma_q : \mathbf{a}_1 + \mathbf{a}_2 = \mathbf{b}_1 + \mathbf{b}_2\}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

Observe that the maximum number of solutions of the above discrete equation is $\lesssim q^{\frac{3n}{2}}$, as a specific triple $(\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{b}_1)$ fixes \mathbf{b}_2 .

In view of this, let us consider the case when the fourth moment is large. Namely assume that for all R large enough, one has

$$M_{E,4}(R) \gtrsim R^{\frac{n}{2}}. \tag{3.15}$$

This condition is tantamount to saying that the discrete equation in (3.14) has the maximum order of magnitude for the number of solutions: $\gtrsim q^{\frac{n}{2}}$.

Then we can establish the principal result of this section; before we do this let us introduce some definitions.

- We say that a finite set \mathbb{A} is an *arithmetic progression* in \mathbb{Z}^n of dimension D and size L , if each element of $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{A}$ possesses a representation

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathbf{g}_0 + \{r_1 \mathbf{g}_1 + \cdots + r_k \mathbf{g}_D\}_{1 \leq r_j \leq L_j}, \tag{3.16}$$

where each r_j is an integer, each \mathbf{g}_j is a (fixed) element of \mathbb{Z}^n (called a generator), and $L_1 \cdot L_2 \cdot \cdots \cdot L_D = L$. An arithmetic progression is *proper* if the representation (3.16) is unique for each $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{A}$.

- Let us call a measure μ , satisfying (3.1) and supported on a compact set E *arithmetic* if there exists a positive measure subset $E' \subset E$, such that for each δ sufficiently small, E'_δ , the δ -neighborhood of E' is contained in some 10δ -neighborhood of a dilate of a proper arithmetic progression $\mathbb{A} = \mathbb{A}(\delta)$ in \mathbb{Z}^n . (If $\alpha > 0$, the progression has to get longer as $\delta \rightarrow 0$.)

Theorem 3.1. *If (3.15) holds for all sufficiently large R , the measure μ is arithmetic.*

The condition (3.15) is in particular satisfied in the case $n = 2$, when E is the boundary of a polygon, which certainly satisfies Theorem 3.1.

Theorem 3.1 will follow from the following classical combinatorial theorem, see [8], [5].

Theorem 3.2 (Freiman’s theorem). *Let $A, B \subset \mathbb{Z}^n$ such that $|A| = |B| = q$, and $|A + B| \leq Cq$, where C is independent of q and*

$$A + B = \{\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{a} \in A, \mathbf{b} \in B\}.$$

Then A is contained in some D -dimensional arithmetic progression in \mathbb{Z}^n , where D depends only on C .

Freiman’s theorem can be applied to (3.14, 3.15) as follows. By the Balog-Szemerédi-Gowers theorem, see e.g [21], since the equation (3.14) has the maximum possible order of the number of solutions, there exists a subset Γ'_q of cardinality of $\gtrsim |\Gamma_q|$, such that the cardinality of $\Gamma'_q + \Gamma'_q$ is $\lesssim |\Gamma'_q|$, the hidden constants being independent of q . Clearly, the set Γ'_q cannot have diameter $o(q)$, as this would contradict (3.1): one cannot have a positive proportion of the elements of Γ_q inside a set whose volume is $o(1)$. The Freiman theorem is now applied to the set Γ'_q , and this proves Theorem 3.1. The estimate on the dimension of the progression (although quite horrendous in terms of the constants involved) is nevertheless independent of q and thus δ .

Let us consider the opposite case to the presence of strong additive structure on E . Namely, we say that a measure μ on E is *strictly convex* if the equation

$$\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{y}', \quad \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}' \in E \tag{3.17}$$

has an at most bounded number of non-trivial solutions, i.e. those when \mathbf{x} is not equal \mathbf{x}' or \mathbf{y}' .

Let us show that the Falconer conjecture holds for strictly convex measures. That is we have to prove that $M_{E,2} \lesssim 1$. By Cauchy-Schwartz we have

$$\begin{aligned} M_{E,2} \lesssim M_{E,4} &\lesssim R^n \mu^* \{(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}') : \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y} = R^{-1} \mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{y}'\}, \\ &\lesssim R^{n-2\alpha} \lesssim 1, \end{aligned} \tag{3.18}$$

for $\alpha \geq \frac{n}{2}$, as desired. We conclude that an “anti-additive” case, i.e. when the discrete equation in (3.14) has the minimum number of solutions, the fourth moment $M_{E,4}$ is small enough, to render the Falconer conjecture. On the other hand, when $M_{E,4}$ is as large as possible, it appears feasible to use Theorem 3.1 to establish the Falconer conjecture for arithmetic measures, by perhaps extending the approach whereby this is done for lattices.

Returning to material fingerprinting, the pair of moments $M_{E,2}$ and $M_{E,4}$ represent important information regarding the distance and addition structure of the sample set E , and therefore are likely to identify promptly different types of translational symmetry of crystal matter. The same can be said about higher moments $M_{E,2l}$, $l > 2$, which would yield the discrete equation

$$\mathbf{a}_1 + \cdots + \mathbf{a}_l = \mathbf{b}_1 + \cdots + \mathbf{b}_l,$$

cf. (3.14). In particular, Theorem 3.1 applies to higher moments. In view of this we suggest that an array of moments $\{M_{E,2l}\}_{l \geq 1}$ should represent a trustworthy signature of a given crystalline material.

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